

protons of the carbon skeleton were comparable to that reported⁷ in the case of 4,2'-dihydroxy-4'-methoxychalcone. Methylation and acetylation yielded the anticipated trimethyl ether⁸ (2b) and triacetate⁸ (2c), respectively; and their physical data agreed with those reported. The ¹³C{¹H} nmr (90 MHz, DMSO-d₆) spectrum of compound 2a, together with the off-resonance spectrum, showed signals at δ 191.26 (s, CO), 165.57 (s, C-2'), 164.81 (s, C-4'), 160.05 (s, C-4), 144.01 (d, C-β), 132.47 (d, C-6'), 130.90 (d, C-2, 6), 125.54 (s, C-1'), 117.14 (d, C-α), 115.67 (d, C-3, 5), 112.81 (s, C-1'), 107.98 (d, C-5) and 102.45 (d, C-3'); comparable to the signals due to the skeletal carbon atoms of the model compound 2'-hydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxychalcone⁹; nevertheless the anticipated⁹ six-line multiplet of C-α and C-β in the off-resonance spectrum could be observed only as doublets.

Compound 3a (0.009%); m.p. 207°, [α]_D -26° (c 0.99 in MeOH); C₁₈H₁₈O₆, M⁺ 256; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650 cm⁻¹ (CO); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) (log ϵ) 240 sh, 280 (4.30), 314 nm (1.72), was characterised as 7,4'-dihydroxyflavanone (liquiritigenin) as the reported m.p.¹⁰ and uv data⁹ agreed with the observed, and it gave a deep violet colour in the Shinoda test¹¹. The ¹H nmr spectrum of the compound 3a was in agreement with the spectrum reported⁷ for liquiritigenin. Methylation and acetylation of compound 3a resulted in the anticipated dimethyl ether (3b)¹² and diacetate (3c)¹⁰, respectively. In the ¹³C{¹H} nmr (90 MHz, DMSO-d₆) spectrum of the compound 3a, the signals due to the skeletal carbon atoms were comparable to that reported⁹ for 7,4'-dimethoxyflavanone. The off-resonance spectrum showed multiplicities supporting the assignments. The spectrum showed signals at δ 189.85 (s, CO), 164.33 (s, C-7), 162.86 (s, C-8a), 157.28 (s, C-4'), 129.06 (s, C-1'), 128.14 (d, C-5), 127.98 (d, C-2', 6'), 114.86 (s, C-4a), 113.29 (d, C-3', 5'), 110.20 (d, C-6), 102.29 (d, C-8), 78.72 (d, C-2), and 42.91 (t, C-3).

It is notable that optically active liquiritigenin has been isolated in the present investigation. Earlier workers¹³ who employed the method of alkali extraction and subsequent acidification for the isolation of this compound from several *Pterocarpus* woods, appears to have obtained a racemic form of it.

Acknowledgement

We wish to express our thanks to Prof. C. V. Ratnam and Prof. G. Srimannarayana, Department of Chemistry, Osmania University for helpful discussions.

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Sterols of *Salsola foetida*†

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Manuscript received 13 February 1984, revised 2 May 1984, accepted 30 May 1984

In the Ayurvedic system of medicine *Salsola foetida* (Chenopodiaceae) is highly used as vermifuge and the ashes of the plant are applied to itches¹. Some alkaloids have earlier been detected in *Salsola* species², but no report was found on their phyto-sterol composition. The chemical examination of the light petroleum extract of *S. foetida* has now resulted in the isolation of five sterols.

Experimental

Air-dried and powdered plant material (820 g) was extracted thrice with light petroleum for 36 h under reflux. After the usual work up light petroleum extract gave 5.32 g neutral extract, which after purification was subjected to column chromatographic separation over silica gel (~25 fold excess). Elution with light petroleum ether: benzene (1:1) gave a sterol fraction which exhibited positive Liberman-Burchard test and gave yellow colour with tetranitromethane. Its ir spectrum (KBr) revealed the presence of OH (1040, 3400 cm⁻¹) and C=C (1610 cm⁻¹) groups. It was crystallised from methanol and gave shining flakes, m.p. 130-32° (tlc-homogeneous, silica gel-5% AgNO₃, using several solvent systems). Since it was not found to be identical (m.m.p., co-tlc) with the available authentic specimen of sterols it was supposed to be a mixture which could not be separated further even by repeated column chromatography. For final confirmation the sterol fraction was then acetylated (Ac₂O-pyridine) and identification of each component was

† Presented in 20th Annual Convention of Chemists held at Guttack, December, 1983.

carried out by comparison with authentic sterol acetate of the R_f on argentation tlc and relative retention time on glc.

Glc was performed on OV-17 on SCOT glass capillary column (30 m × 0.3 mm i.d.) at 255°, injection at 275° and nitrogen carrier gas at 0.60 ml/min (split ratio ca. 100 : 1). RRT in glc was given relative to cholesteryl acetate. The other techniques used in the present work have been described previously⁸. The sterol acetates were shown to contain five phytosterols. The approximate content of each sterol in the acetylated total sterol fraction as determined by glc was : 24 β -methylcholesta-5,22-dien-3 β -ol acetate (brassicasterol, 12.3%) ; (24 ξ)-24-methylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol acetate (campesterol, 5.2%) ; (22E, 24 ξ)-24-ethylcholesta-5,22-dien-3 β -ol acetate (stigmasterol, 36.9%) ; (24 ξ)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol acetate (β -sitosterol, 29.9%) ; and 24-ethylcholest-5,24-dien-3 β -ol (15.7%) of RRT 1.96.

Discussion

It is known that three phytosterols (β -sitosterol, campesterol and stigmasterol) form the major components of sterols in many plants⁴⁻⁶. The number of sterols found in *Salsola foetida* is five, which include relatively large amounts of 24-ethylcholesta-5,24-dienol (15.7% of the total sterol) and brassicasterol (12.3%). The former sterol was first identified in *Withania somnifera*⁶ and the later in *Solanaceous* seeds⁷. It was recently reported⁸ to form biosynthetic intermediate for $\Delta^{2,4(8)}$ -sterol to 24-alkylated sterol conversion.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. S. C. Gupta, Principal and Dr. M. Behari, Head of the Chemistry Department, S. V. College, Aligarh for providing facilities. Sincere thanks are due to T. Matsumoto, Nihon University, Japan for glc analysis. Thanks are also due to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship (K.K.).

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Chemical Investigation of *Lonicera maacki*

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Manuscript received 18 April 1983, revised 19 March 1984,
accepted 26 May 1984

THE present investigation on the leaves of *Lonicera maacki* (Caprifoliaceae) resulted in the isolation and characterisation of three known compounds. In addition, the presence of three more biflavones have been indicated by tlc examination of methylated products.

Air dried and powdered leaves (1 kg) of *Lonicera maacki* was soxhleted with petroleum ether, benzene and chloroform successively for 3 h each. The residue after treatment with petroleum ether and benzene was chromatographed over silica gel using benzene : pyridine : formic acid (36 : 9 : 5) as solvent¹ for separation. Tlc revealed the presence of six bands.

The first compound (80 mg), R_f 0.18, m.p. 322°, was characterised as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7 hexahydroxy (I-3', II-8) biflavone (amentoflavone). On methylation with dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone it gave colourless crystals of hexa-O-methyl amentoflavone, m.p. 181-82°, (CHCl₃ - MeOH) R_f 0.40. Acetylation (Ac₂O/pyridine) of the compound yielded amentoflavone hexaacetate and crystallisation from CHCl₃ - MeOH gave colourless needles, m.p. 242-43°. The identity was confirmed by the comparison of ¹H-nmr spectra of the derivatives (methylether and acetate) with those of the authentic samples².

The second compound, m.p. 349° (MeOH) was identified as 5,7,4'-trihydroxy flavone and on methylation with dimethyl sulphate gave a trimethyl ether, m.p. 155°. It was characterised as apigenin by chromatographic and spectral comparison with an authentic sample³.

The third flavanone, m.p. 228° gave an intense pink colour with Zn/HCl. Its identity with naringenin was established by direct comparison of the acetate and methyl ether with those of the authentic sample⁴.

Tlc examination of the methylated product of the other three bands showed them to be identical with amentoflavone hexamethyl ether both in R_f value and colour. Tlc of the parent compounds indicated them to be mono-, di- and tri-O-methyl amentoflavone.

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